

COMPOSITE MONOCOQUE FRAME FOR BICYCLES, THE DESIGN AND THE FABRICATION

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ABSTRACT

A new simple design scheme and a new fabrication technique for one-piece composite monocoque bicycle frames are presented. A user-friendly computer design program for the composite bicycle frames is developed. A group of possible design solutions for each portion of the frame are determined and stored as a matrix in the program. The program performs basic calculations using the design conditions given by the user, and selects the best design solution from the matrix and shows the results to the user. Pressurized bladders are frequently used to create a light-weight shell structure in bicycle frames. In this study, a simple new method of pressurizing the bladder is developed, which does not need an open end nor a special device prepared on the mold. Composite tooling is utilized to fabricate the monocoque frame.

Keywords : monocoque, bicycle frames, user-friendly computer program, design, fabrication, pressurizing bladder, composite tooling

1. INTRODUCTION

The frame of a bicycle is a critical part which can decide the final performance of the bicycle since it supports the whole structure like a spine. It should be strong enough to support the load and the impacts during normal or off-the-road riding. It should have adequate flexibility which can absorb the vibration during riding and give the rider a comfort feeling without disturbing the alignment of the whole structure which is very important to minimize the energy loss.

Carbon steels have been the major fabricating material in conventional bicycle frames. Materials like aluminum-alloys, Cr-Mo steels, or Ti-alloys are being applied in high-priced bicycles. Currently, the development of monocoque composite frame seems to be the major trend in the bicycle industries. The performance of composite bicycle has proven to be extraordinary in many international competitions like olympic games, and the ability for a bicycle company to build a fine composite bicycle is believed to be the reflection of the high technology of the manufacturer.

frame. Design process of a composite bicycle frame needs a group of composite experts to perform complicated FEM analysis and calculations on the anisotropic composite materials to decide the fiber placement angles and the number of plies to meet the design specifications. It is, however, difficult for a medium-to-small sized bicycle company to maintain a resident group of composite experts in the company. Hence, a user-friendly computer design program which can be used easily by the bicycle companies to design composite bicycle frames is needed to accelerate the application of the composite materials in bicycle industries.

In this study, an easy-to-use computer program is developed, which can suggest an initial design of a composite bicycle frame. The program performs the design based on the stress analysis rather than the strain analysis. Since the riding performance of a bicycle depends upon the flexibility of the frame, the initial design based on the strength should be checked and modified through the FEM analysis in view of the strain. Shown in Figure 2 is the simplified flow chart of the computer program used in this study.

Figure 2. Flow Chart of the Design Program

Parts in a composite bicycle frame, such as top tube, down tube ... etc., has some limit conditions due to the weight and productivity of the fabrication process. The limiting conditions are, for instance, the maximum and minimum number of plies and the angle of fiber placement. Taking four as the minimum number of plies in a composite frame part will not be unreasonable because when the number of plies becomes smaller than four, it is physically difficult to produce the part and

guarantee the safe performance against a concentrated stress or a sudden impact. Since it is expected that the composite frames should be lighter than the carbon steel frames, the maximum number of plies can also be located reasonably from design and manufacturing experiences. The orientation of the fiber placement can also be simplified to several combinations of $[0]$, $[90]$, $[\pm 45]$, or $[\pm a]$ in the range of the maximum and minimum number of plies considering the productivity of the material lay-up process.

In the computer program developed in this study, a table of possible design solutions for each portion of the frame are prepared by the composite and the bicycle design experts and stored as a matrix. The selection of the fiber orientation and the lay-up sequence has been done in the range of the limiting conditions chosen by the composite experts and the manufacturer. The section shapes of the frame tubes are idealized to several kinds of oval shapes or circles. The program performs stress calculations using the design conditions given by the user, and selects the best design solution for each part of the frame from the matrix by comparing the result of the calculation with the pre-stored matrix, and shows the results to the user.

The flexibility of the frame is also a very important factor since this affects the riding performance significantly. The initial design based on the strength was checked and modified through the FEM analysis in view of the strain. The FEM analysis was performed using NISA II - Composite FEM package. Three-dimensional beam element, which was thought to be enough to simulate the distortion of the frame, was used to simplify the analysis procedure so that the bicycle companies can follow the procedure later in real production of various kinds of frames without difficulty.

In the analysis, 95 node FEM model was used with 97 three-dimensional beam element of 2 nodes. Since the composite lay-up of a bicycle frame is normally symmetric and the lay-up sequence is the combination of the four angles $[0]$, $[45]$, $[90]$, $[-45]$, and the beam element was used, the axial stiffness, poisson's ratio, density, and thermal expansion coefficients are the main inputs. Hence the equivalent isotropic material constants of the Carbon/Epoxy beams were used as the material constants for the analysis. The FEM analysis procedure was constructed as a macro file so that bicycle companies can use it to develop various kinds of frames just by changing the input factors.

3. THE FABRICATION

3.1 Process

Pressurized bladders are frequently used to create a light-weight shell structure in bicycle frames. The schematic diagram of the process using a bladder is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Composite manufacturing process using a bladder

The prepreg in the mold is pushed tightly to the wall by the bladder expanded by the compressed air while appropriate heat is applied to the mold to cure the prepreg. This process produces high quality composite parts with a good surface and little voids in it, and the products show good mechanical characteristics. However, when making bicycle frames using this method, special devices are needed to be prepared on the mold to connect the pressurized air to the bladder through the open ends of the frame. The design of the mold and the fabrication process including bladder placement, lay-up of the prepreg in the mold, and insertion of the lugs and other parts becomes complicated. In this study, a simple new method to supply the compressed air to the bladder is developed. Shown in Figure 4 is the schematic diagram of the method.

Figure 4. A method to supply compressed air to the bladder

This technique does not need an open end in the part nor a special device prepared on the mold. Only a small hole drilled on the mold is sufficient. Since small sized holes can be located virtually at any part of the composite frame, the design of the bladder lay out becomes very easy and takes little time.

3.2 Composite Tooling

Composite tooling is utilized to fabricate the monocoque frame. Since FRP molds are less expensive and the time to make or repair the mold is much shorter compared to steel molds, it is a good choice to use FRP mold when developing a new process or a new product which needs frequent modification of the mold. The FRP mold developed in this study was made using high cure-temperature epoxy and carbon fabric. The mold was cured at 140°C and post cured at 180°C to get thermal stability at the temperature of 140 °C which is the curing temperature of the prepreg used to fabricate the frame. Shown in Figure 5 is the FRP mold developed in this study.

Figure 5. FRP mold

3.3 The prototype

The developed prototype composite monocoque frame is shown in Figure 6. The weight of the frame was 1.7 kg.

Figure 6. Prototype frame

The developed composite frames successfully passed the vibration, impact, drop weight, and energy absorption tests. The road test and distortion test were also performed on the frames as performance

verification tests. Table 1 shows the safety test specifications, and Figure 7 shows the vibration test being done.

Table 1. Safety test specifications

Tests	Load	Conditions
Impact Test	Seat : 120kgf	-Front wheel center drop height is 30 mm with rear wheel center hinged. -Repeat 10,000 times -Frequency : 250 RPM
Vibration Test	Seat : 45kgf Hanger : 15 kgf	-Frequency : 460 RPM -Number of cycles : 70,000 -Acceleration : 19.6 m/S ² (2G)
Drop Weight Test	M=22.5	-Height : 180 mm -Drop weight along a vertical line which passes through the front and the rear wheel centers.
Energy absorption Test	Up to 880 N (90 kgf)	-Compression load applied between the front and the rear wheel centers. -Total energy absorption must exceed 40 Joules.

Figure 7. Vibration test

4. CONCLUSION

A monocoque composite bicycle frame is developed using a new design technique and a new fabrication process. a simple new method to build the inner-pressure in the bladder during the fabrication process is utilized. This new technique does not need an open end nor a special device prepared on the mold. A new design scheme is also used in this study. An easy-to-use computer program for the design of composite bicycle frames is developed. This simple design process can expand the use of the composite materials in the bicycle industry.

FRP tooling was utilized in producing the prototype composite frame. With the FRP tooling it was possible to reduce the development cost and time and the modification of the mold became very easy during the development process. The weight of the developed monocoque composite bicycle frame was 1.7 kg which is similar to other manufacturers' products. The frames developed in this study successfully passed the vibration, impact, weight-drop, and energy absorption tests. The road test and distortion tests were also performed on the frames as performance verification tests.

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